

EFFECT OF RESTAURANT ATTRIBUTES ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

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Abstract

Introduction: The restaurant industry is growing rapidly and is one of the trending businesses around the world. The phenomenal escalation of the restaurant industry offers customers enticing, delicious snacks along with a calm environment and good atmosphere. **Objective:** The objective of this study was to assess customer satisfaction with the different characteristics of Faisalabad restaurants. **Methodology:** A cross-sectional study was conducted on 200 respondents. Data was collected through a convenient sampling technique from different restaurants in Faisalabad by a modified questionnaire of the DINESERV model according to the present study. The statistical analysis was determined through SPSS V22 by applying the Pearson correlation between customer satisfaction and restaurant characteristics. **Results:** There were 56% females and 46% males in the given study. Most of the respondents were in the age group of 16-25 and 172 individuals were married. Most of the participants (178 and 175) were satisfied with the quality of the food and service of the restaurants while 95 individuals showed dissatisfaction with the location of the restaurants. **Conclusion:** The study showed a strong positive correlation between customer satisfaction and the quality of food and the service quality of the restaurants while a weak positive correlation between customer satisfaction and the location of the restaurants.

Keywords: Food Quality, Service Quality, Ambiance of Restaurant, Customer Satisfaction.

1. INTRODUCTION

The restaurant industry is growing rapidly and is one of the trending businesses around the world. They provide good service and provide high-quality food to their customers. Every restaurant rests on three basic attributes, which are food, service, and physical environment.

Customers expect a certain level of quality against these attributes provided by the respective restaurant [1]. Providing high-quality food in a pleasant dining environment and courteous service to all guests are key elements of any restaurant industry.

A customer usually goes to restaurants that have a stimulating environment to fulfill their desire for entertainment along with the basic urge known as hunger. Diners are increasingly being modernized and improved in terms of decor, ambiance, and interior design to attract customers and differentiate themselves from their competitors such as fast food restaurants [2]. Currently, the food restaurant market, one of the emerging industries in Pakistan, is intensively changing the standard of living [3].

In addition, fast food chains are working hard to attract customers by providing quality food, competitive prices, diversified food products, and better services so that the customers will visit them again after being satisfied with their experience. In addition, there will be enough trained and qualified staff from waiters to managers to provide good services to consumers [4].

Consumers cognitively evaluate their experiences while dining at restaurants. Food quality, staff service, environment, and hygienic conditions are the main components when evaluating restaurant services [5]. In a restaurant setting, after food quality, food variety, and price, it is an atmosphere that is considered the main element that differentiates one service provider from another.

Thus, it can be said that atmosphere has become essential in restaurant settings as customers tend to be provoked by atmospheric cues such as lights, atmosphere, style, cleanliness, comfortable seats, aesthetic elements, music, and noise, which in turn increases the behavior of intentional or repeated patronage [6]. Food quality is one of the important factors affecting customer satisfaction. It is accredited as a determinant of customer visits to the restaurant.

Food quality depends on food taste, menu, presentation, freshness, variety, and health. Food plays a key role in the restaurant experience and its taste, presentation, textures, colors, temperature, freshness, nutritional value, and aroma are identified as important quality attributes for restaurant guests. Portion size and menu variety are considered determinants of food enjoyment [7].

2. METHODOLOGY

A cross-sectional study was conducted in different restaurants in Faisalabad, Pakistan for four months; March-June, 2024. A total of 200 respondents (56% females and 44% male) aged between 16-55 years were selected via a convenient sampling technique, calculated by the OpenEpi software.

The individuals who gave consent and were over the age of 15 years were included in the study. However, individuals who refused to participate and were younger than 15 years of age were excluded from the study. The data was collected by the slightly modified DINESERV model questionnaire according to the parameters of the given study, comprising two sections. Section I has demographic features such as age, gender, and marital status of the customers.

Section II yields customer satisfaction on the quality of the food, atmosphere/ambiance of the restaurant, service quality of the restaurant, price of food in the restaurants, and the location of the restaurant. The statistical analysis was determined through SPSS V22 by applying the Pearson Correlation between customer satisfaction and the quality of the food, atmosphere/ambiance of the restaurant, service quality of the restaurant, price of food in the restaurants, and the location of the restaurant.

There were no ethical issues in this study because the individuals were not put on the experiment and no medication was given during the study. Moreover, the study was duly approved by the ethical committee.

3. RESULTS

Figure 1 demonstrates the distribution of individuals according to the gender. 56% of the respondents were female while 44% were male subjects.

Figure 1: Distribution of the respondents according to their gender

The age group of the respondents is depicted in Table 1. 100 respondents were in the age group 16-25, 55 were in the 26-35 age group, 35 were in the age group 36-45, and only 10 were in the 46-55 years of age group.

Table 1: Distribution of the respondents according to their age group

Respondents	Frequency	Percentage
16-25	100	50%
26-35	55	27.5%
36-45	35	17.5%
46-55	10	5%
Total	200	100%

Figure 2 illustrates the marital status of respondents. Out of 200, 172 respondents were married while 28 respondents were single.

Figure 2: Distribution of the respondents according to marital status

Table 2 describes the relationship between the variables and the customer satisfaction. Out of 200 respondents, 178 (89%) were satisfied with the quality of food of the restaurants while 22 (11%) were not satisfied.

Out of 200 respondents, 175 (87%) were satisfied with the atmosphere/ambiance of the restaurants while 25 (13%) were not satisfied. Out of 200 respondents, 171 (85%) were satisfied with the service of quality offered by the restaurants while 29 (15%) were not satisfied.

Out of 200 respondents, 158 (79%) were satisfied with the restaurants' food prices while 41 (21%) showed dissatisfaction. Out of 200 respondents, 105 (53%) were satisfied with the location of the restaurants while 95 (47%) were not satisfied.

Table 2: Distribution of the variables and customer satisfaction

Variables	Customer Satisfaction			
	Yes		No	
	F	%	F	%
Quality of Food	178	89%	22	11%
Atmosphere / Ambiance of Restaurant	175	87%	25	13%
Service Quality of Restaurant	171	85%	29	15%
Price of Food	159	79%	41	21%
Location of Restaurant	105	53%	95	47%

Table 3 describes the Pearson correlation between the variables and customer satisfaction. There was a strong positive correlation between the quality of food of the restaurants and customer satisfaction with $r=1$ and $\alpha < 0.01$.

There was a strong positive correlation between the atmosphere/ambiance of the restaurants and customer satisfaction with $r=0.96$ and $\alpha < 0.01$. There was a strong positive correlation between the service of quality offered by the restaurants and customer satisfaction with $r=0.96$ and $\alpha < 0.01$.

There was a moderate positive correlation between the restaurants' food prices and customer satisfaction with $r=0.89$ and $\alpha < 0.03$. However, there was a weak positive correlation between the location of the restaurants and customer satisfaction with $r=0.47$ and $\alpha > 0.05$.

Table 3: Pearson Correlation variables and customer satisfaction

Variables	Customer Satisfaction				r
	Yes		No		
	F	%	F	%	
Quality of Food	178	89%	22	11%	1
Atmosphere / Ambiance of Restaurant	175	87%	25	13%	0.96
Service Quality of Restaurant	171	85%	29	15%	0.96
Price of Food	159	79%	41	21%	0.89
Location of Restaurant	105	53%	95	47%	0.47

4. DISCUSSION

The current study was conducted in Faisalabad to assess customer satisfaction on various attributes of fast food restaurants. 56% of the respondents were female while 44% were male subjects in the given study. 40% of respondents aged 16-25 participated in the Study and most of the subjects (75.5%) were students.

Sanjeev Kumar and his colleague determined the effect of food and service quality on customer satisfaction in 2017. The study was conducted in different hotels in Punjab, India on 150 subjects. It was found most of the subjects were male (76%), and most of participants were of age group 25-34 years.

Food quality and customer satisfaction are highly correlated with each other ($p=0.000$). There was also a strong relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction [8]. A survey was conducted to evaluate various food service features that influence customer satisfaction at the university cafeteria.

A convenient sampling technique was used to select 676 subjects over 5 weeks. Service quality and quality of food were assessed through a questionnaire with closed questions. Pearson correlation coefficients were used to measure the degree of significant relationship between dependent and independent variables. It was found all attributes had significant effect on customer satisfaction.

62.9% of customers like to continue eating from the cafeteria along with suggestions for improving diet quality by the addition of more nutritious food [9].

Another study was conducted by Rozekhi et al (2016) to determine the influence of food quality on customers. Self-administered questionnaires having close-ended questions were distributed among selected subjects of Malaysia.

The convenient sampling technique was used to collect data from 100 respondents. Most of the subjects were 31-40 years of age and 69.1% were married. The relationship between food quality attributes and overall satisfaction was assessed through multiple regression. It was found that customers were significantly affected by food quality features ($\beta= 0.709$) [10].

Similarly, the effect of fast food restaurant service quality and its dimensions on customer perception, satisfaction, and behavioral intention were analyzed by Slack and his colleagues in 2021. Data was collected from 400 customers and the study used descriptive and inferential analysis. Results showed all features were statistically significant ($p=0.01$) [11].

5. CONCLUSION

The study showed that the food and service quality of the restaurants was good and enhanced customer satisfaction. Every restaurant lies on three basic attributes i.e. quality of food, service quality of the restaurant, and environment/ambiance of the restaurant. Customers expect a certain level of quality against these attributes that are provided by the restaurants.

The impact of restaurant characteristics on customer satisfaction was assessed and most of the customers were satisfied with the quality of the food and service quality of the restaurants exhibiting the strong positive correlation between these.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest

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